

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Ceres Second Extension Elliptical (C2E) (vir_da945)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da945 session. These operations were executed as part of the C2E phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Ceres, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da945 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis et al., "The VIR Spectrometer," *ISSR*, vol. 163, no. 1–4, pp. 329–369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_c2e_C4S1LOW.r02.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_c2e_C4S1LOW.r02.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_c2e_c4s1LOW.r02.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_C2E_YMLSTART_C4S1LOW	589060248	589060250	2
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_075	589060308	589060729	421
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_075	589060908	589070814	9906
VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075	589071768	589073582	1814
VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_075	589073868	589073908	40
VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075	589073988	589075582	1594
VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_075	589075638	589075676	38
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_075	589075758	589075765	7
VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_075	589075818	589080318	4500
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_075	589080318	589080618	300
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_076	589160673	589161094	421
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_076	589161273	589171179	9906
VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_076	589172133	589172173	40
VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076	589172253	589173847	1594
VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_076	589173903	589173941	38
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_076	589173998	589174005	7
VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_076	589174058	589178558	4500
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_076	589178558	589178858	300
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_077	589259013	589259434	421
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_077	589259613	589269519	9906
VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_077	589270473	589270513	40
VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077	589270593	589272187	1594
VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_077	589272243	589272281	38
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_077	589272338	589272345	7
VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_077	589272398	589276898	4500
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_077	589276898	589277198	300
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_078	589357406	589357827	421
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_078	589358006	589367912	9906
VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_078	589368866	589368906	40
VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078	589368986	589370580	1594
VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_078	589370636	589370674	38
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_078	589370731	589370738	7
VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_078	589370791	589375291	4500
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_078	589375291	589375591	300
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_079	589455820	589456241	421
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_079	589456420	589466326	9906
VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_079	589467280	589467320	40
VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079	589467400	589468994	1594
VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_079	589469050	589469088	38
VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_079	589469145	589469152	7

VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_079	589469205	589473705	4500
VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_079	589474305	589474605	300
VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C4S1LOW	589474665	589474666	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Integrated sequence: da945c.00.filter.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da945c.00.filter.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 2 calibration cubes and 10 cubes for IR channel and 0 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

3. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

3.1 The sequence: vir_c2e_C4S1LOW.r02.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_c2e_C4S1LOW.r02.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2018-242T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2018-274T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2018-218T07:45:36.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_c2e_C4S1LOW.r02;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Mon Aug 06 07:45:36 2018
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2018-242T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2018-274T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_C2E_DA945_ds674
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *C2E_PERIAP_075, 2018-244T10:59:48.000
26 *C2E_PERIAP_076, 2018-245T14:17:33.000
27 *C2E_PERIAP_077, 2018-246T17:36:33.000
28 *C2E_PERIAP_078, 2018-247T20:56:26.000
29 *C2E_PERIAP_079, 2018-249T00:16:40.000
30 *EPOCHS_END
31 *Input files used:
32 *File Type  Last modified          File name
33 *****
34 $$EOH
35 $$EOD
36
37 request(VIR_C2E_VMLSTART_C4S1LOW,
38         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075-03:09:00,
39         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_c2e_C4S1LOW (ds674)",
40         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
41         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
42         KEY, "No_Key")
43
44     activity(1,
45             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
46
47             SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds674","ds674.n
48             fb04")
49         ),
50     note(1,
51         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
52         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds674 - vir_c2e_C4S1LOW"\
53     ),
54 end;

```

```

53
54  request(VIR_C2E_C4S1Power0n_075,
55          START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075-03:08:00,
56          TITLE, "VIR Power on",
57          REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
58          PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
59          KEY, "No_Key")
60
61  spawn(1,
62        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
63        REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
64        RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
65        ),
66  note(1,
67        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
68        TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1Power0n_075: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
69        ),
70  end;
71
72  request(VIR_C2E_C4S1Cryocooler0n_075,
73          START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075-02:58:00,
74          TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
75          REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
76          PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
77          KEY, "No_Key")
78
79  command(1,
80          SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
81          NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1Cryocooler0n_075: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
82          VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
83          ),
84  command(2,
85          SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
86          NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1Cryocooler0n_075: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
87          VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
88          ),
89  note(1,
90          SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
91          TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1Cryocooler0n_075: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3
92          hour waiting."\<
93  end;
94
95  request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075,
96          START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075+00:03:00,
97          TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
98          REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
99          PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
100         KEY, "No_Key")
101
102  command(1,
103          SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
104          NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\<,
105          VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
106          ),
107  command(2,
108          SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

```

```
109     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075: perform the internal full calibration"\,  
110     VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F","CLOSECOVERATEND","FULLCALSEQ")  
111     ),  
112     command(3,  
113     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
114     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075: select VIR on 1553 bus"\,  
115     XB_SELECT_INSTRUMENT("VIR")  
116     ),  
117     command(4,  
118     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:02\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
119     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075: begin data dumping into VR4."\  
120     VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")  
121     ),  
122     command(5,  
123     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
124     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\  
125     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
126     ),  
127     note(1,  
128     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
129     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075: full calibration is finished."\  
130     ),  
131     note(2,  
132     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
133     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CalibrationDump_075: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit, 120 pages, 15960  
134     packets."\  
135     end;  
136  
137     request(VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_075,  
138     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075+00:38:00,  
139     TITLE, "VIR open cover",  
140     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
141     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
142     KEY, "No_Key")  
143  
144     activity(1,  
145     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
146     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_075: Set for opening the cover."\  
147     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")  
148     ),  
149     end;  
150  
151     request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075,  
152     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075+00:40:00,  
153     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",  
154     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
155     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
156     KEY, "No_Key")  
157  
158     command(1,  
159     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
160     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1  
161     detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\  
162     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V  
163     ),  
164     command(2,
```

```

164     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
165     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\",
166     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
167     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
168   ),
169   command(3,
170     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
171     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
172     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
173   ),
174   note(1,
175     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
176     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit\"
177   ),
178   command(4,
179     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
180     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
181     detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s\",
182     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,\"IR_ONLY\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_V
183   ),
184   command(5,
185     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
186     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\",
187     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
188     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
189   ),
190   command(6,
191     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
192     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
193     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
194   ),
195   note(2,
196     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
197     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_075: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"
198   ),
199   end;
200   request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_075,
201     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075+01:07:30,
202     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
203     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
204     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
205     KEY, \"No_Key\")
206
207   activity(1,
208     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
209     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_075: Set for closing the cover.\"\",
210     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
211   ),
212   end;
213
214   request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_075,
215     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075+01:09:30,
216     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
217     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
218     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
219     KEY, \"No_Key\")

```

```
220
221     command(1,
222         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
223         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_075: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
224         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
225     ),
226     command(2,
227         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
228         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_075: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
229         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
230     ),
231     note(1,
232         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
233         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_075: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
234     ),
235 end;
236
237 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_075,
238     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075+01:10:30,
239     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
240     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
241     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
242     KEY, "No_Key")
243
244     command(1,
245         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
246         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\\,
247         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_075: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
248         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
249     ),
250     command(2,
251         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
252         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_075: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
253         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
254     ),
255     note(1,
256         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
257         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_075: data volume in VR4 0.664 Gibit.\"\\
258     ),
259 end;
260
261 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_075,
262     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_075+02:25:30,
263     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
264     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
265     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
266     KEY, "No_Key")
267
268     note(1,
269         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
270         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_075: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\
271     ),
272     spawn(1,
273         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
274         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\\,
275         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
276     ),
```

```
277     note(2,  
278         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
279         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_075: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\  
280     ),  
281 end;  
282  
283 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_076,  
284     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_076-02:33:00,  
285     TITLE, \"VIR Power on\",  
286     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
287     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
288     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
289  
290 spawn(1,  
291     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
292     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\  
293     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,\"VIR_P\",\"SAFE\")  
294 ),  
295     note(1,  
296         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
297         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_076: Power on VML sequence is finished;\"\  
298     ),  
299 end;  
300  
301 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_076,  
302     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_076-02:23:00,  
303     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler on\",  
304     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
305     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
306     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
307  
308 command(1,  
309     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
310     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_076: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
311     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
312 ),  
313 command(2,  
314     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
315     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_076: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\  
316     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"CLOSELOOP\",85,0)  
317 ),  
318     note(1,  
319         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
320         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_076: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3  
321         hour waiting.\"\  
322     ),  
322 end;  
323  
324 request(VIR_C2E_C4S10penCover_076,  
325     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_076+00:38:00,  
326     TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",  
327     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
328     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
329     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
330  
331 activity(1,  
332     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
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333     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_076: Set for opening the cover."\\,
334     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
335   ),
336 end;
337
338 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076,
339     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_076+00:40:00,
340     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
341     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
342     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
343     KEY, "No_Key")
344
345     command(1,
346     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
347     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
348     detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\\,
349     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",10,"NO_V
350   ),
351     command(2,
352     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
353     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\\,
354     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
355     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
356   ),
357     command(3,
358     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
359     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
360     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
361   ),
362     note(1,
363     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
364     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\\
365   ),
366     command(4,
367     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
368     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
369     detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\\,
370     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",10,"NO_V
371   ),
372     command(5,
373     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
374     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\\,
375     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
376     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
377   ),
378     command(6,
379     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
380     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
381     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
382   ),
383     note(2,
384     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
385     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_076: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\\
386   ),
387 end;
388

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387 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_076,  
388     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_076+01:07:30,  
389     TITLE, "VIR close cover",  
390     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
391     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
392     KEY, "No_Key")  
393  
394     activity(1,  
395         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
396         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_076: Set for closing the cover."\  
397         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")  
398     ),  
399 end;  
400  
401 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_076,  
402     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_076+01:09:05,  
403     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",  
404     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
405     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
406     KEY, "No_Key")  
407  
408     command(1,  
409         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
410         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_076: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
411         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
412     ),  
413     command(2,  
414         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
415         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_076: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\  
416         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)  
417     ),  
418     note(1,  
419         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
420         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_076: the cryocooling is off."\  
421     ),  
422 end;  
423  
424 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_076,  
425     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_076+01:10:05,  
426     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
427     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
428     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
429     KEY, "No_Key")  
430  
431     command(1,  
432         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
433         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\  
434         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_076: begin data dumping into VR4."\  
435         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")  
436     ),  
437     command(2,  
438         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
439         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_076: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
440         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
441     ),  
442     note(1,  
443         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
```

```
444     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_076: data volume in VR4 1.203 Gibit."\  
445     ),  
446 end;  
447  
448 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_076,  
449     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_076+02:25:05,  
450     TITLE, "VIR Power off",  
451     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
452     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
453     KEY, "No_Key")  
454  
455     note(1,  
456     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
457     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_076: Power off VIR instrument."\  
458     ),  
459     spawn(1,  
460     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
461     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\  
462     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)  
463     ),  
464     note(2,  
465     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
466     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_076: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\  
467     ),  
468 end;  
469  
470 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_077,  
471     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_077-02:33:00,  
472     TITLE, "VIR Power on",  
473     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
474     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
475     KEY, "No_Key")  
476  
477     spawn(1,  
478     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
479     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\  
480     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")  
481     ),  
482     note(1,  
483     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
484     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_077: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\  
485     ),  
486 end;  
487  
488 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_077,  
489     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_077-02:23:00,  
490     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",  
491     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
492     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
493     KEY, "No_Key")  
494  
495     command(1,  
496     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
497     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_077: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
498     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
499     ),  
500     command(2,
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501     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
502     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1Cryocooler0n_077: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\  
503     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)  
504     ),  
505     note(1,  
506     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
507     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1Cryocooler0n_077: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3  
508     hour waiting."\  
509     ),  
510     end;  
511     request(VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_077,  
512     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_077+00:38:00,  
513     TITLE, "VIR open cover",  
514     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
515     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
516     KEY, "No_Key")  
517  
518     activity(1,  
519     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
520     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_077: Set for opening the cover."\  
521     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")  
522     ),  
523     end;  
524  
525     request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077,  
526     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_077+00:40:00,  
527     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",  
528     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
529     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
530     KEY, "No_Key")  
531  
532     command(1,  
533     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
534     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1  
535     detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\  
536     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V  
537     ),  
538     command(2,  
539     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
540     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\  
541     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
542     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
543     ),  
544     command(3,  
545     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
546     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
547     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
548     ),  
549     note(1,  
550     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
551     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\  
552     ),  
553     command(4,  
554     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
555     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1  
556     detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\  
557     )
```

```
555     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
556   ),
557   command(5,
558     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
559     COMMENT,"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
560     NTEXT,\<"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
561     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
562   ),
563   command(6,
564     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
565     NTEXT,\<"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
566     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
567   ),
568   note(2,
569     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
570     TEXT,\<"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_077: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
571   ),
572 end;
573
574 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_077,
575   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_077+01:07:30,
576   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
577   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
578   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
579   KEY, "No_Key")
580
581   activity(1,
582     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
583     NTEXT,\<"VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_077: Set for closing the cover."\,
584     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
585   ),
586 end;
587
588 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_077,
589   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_077+01:09:05,
590   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
591   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
592   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
593   KEY, "No_Key")
594
595   command(1,
596     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
597     NTEXT,\<"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_077: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
598     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
599   ),
600   command(2,
601     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
602     NTEXT,\<"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_077: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\,
603     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
604   ),
605   note(1,
606     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
607     TEXT,\<"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_077: the cryocooling is off."\
608   ),
609 end;
610
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611 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_077,  
612     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_077+01:10:05,  
613     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
614     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
615     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
616     KEY, "No_Key")  
617  
618     command(1,  
619         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
620         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,  
621         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_077: begin data dumping into VR4."\,  
622         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")  
623     ),  
624     command(2,  
625         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
626         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_077: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
627         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
628     ),  
629     note(1,  
630         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
631         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_077: data volume in VR4 1.742 Gibit."\  
632     ),  
633 end;  
634  
635 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_077,  
636     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_077+02:25:05,  
637     TITLE, "VIR Power off",  
638     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
639     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
640     KEY, "No_Key")  
641  
642     note(1,  
643         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
644         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_077: Power off VIR instrument."\  
645     ),  
646     spawn(1,  
647         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
648         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\  
649         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)  
650     ),  
651     note(2,  
652         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
653         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_077: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\  
654     ),  
655 end;  
656  
657 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_078,  
658     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_078-02:33:00,  
659     TITLE, "VIR Power on",  
660     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
661     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
662     KEY, "No_Key")  
663  
664     spawn(1,  
665         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
666         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\  
667         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P", "SAFE")
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668     ),
669     note(1,
670         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
671         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_078: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
672     ),
673 end;
674
675 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_078,
676     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_078-02:23:00,
677     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
678     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
679     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
680     KEY, "No_Key")
681
682     command(1,
683         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
684         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_078: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
685         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
686     ),
687     command(2,
688         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
689         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_078: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
690         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
691     ),
692     note(1,
693         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
694         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_078: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3
695         hour waiting."\"
696     ),
697 end;
698 request(VIR_C2E_C4S10penCover_078,
699     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_078+00:38:00,
700     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
701     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
702     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
703     KEY, "No_Key")
704
705     activity(1,
706         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
707         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S10penCover_078: Set for opening the cover."\",
708         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
709     ),
710 end;
711
712 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078,
713     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_078+00:40:00,
714     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
715     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
716     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
717     KEY, "No_Key")
718
719     command(1,
720         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
721         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
722         detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s\"\",
723         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",10,"NO_V
    
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723     ),
724     command(2,
725         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
726         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
727         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
728         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
729     ),
730     command(3,
731         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
732         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
733         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
734     ),
735     note(1,
736         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
737         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
738     ),
739     command(4,
740         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
741         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
742         detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
743         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
744     ),
745     command(5,
746         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
747         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
748         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
749         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
750     ),
751     command(6,
752         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
753         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
754         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
755     ),
756     note(2,
757         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
758         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_078: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
759     ),
760     end;
761     request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_078,
762         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_078+01:07:30,
763         TITLE, "VIR close cover",
764         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
765         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
766         KEY, "No_Key")
767
768     activity(1,
769         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
770         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_078: Set for closing the cover.""\,
771         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
772     ),
773     end;
774
775     request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_078,
776         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_078+01:09:05,
777         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
778         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
    
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779     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
780     KEY, "No_Key")
781
782     command(1,
783     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
784     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_078: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
785     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
786     ),
787     command(2,
788     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
789     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_078: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\\,
790     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
791     ),
792     note(1,
793     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
794     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_078: the cryocooling is off."\\
795     ),
796 end;
797
798 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_078,
799     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_078+01:10:05,
800     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
801     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
802     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
803     KEY, "No_Key")
804
805     command(1,
806     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
807     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\\,
808     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_078: begin data dumping into VR4."\\,
809     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
810     ),
811     command(2,
812     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
813     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_078: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
814     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
815     ),
816     note(1,
817     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
818     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_078: data volume in VR4 2.281 Gibit."\\
819     ),
820 end;
821
822 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_078,
823     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_078+02:25:05,
824     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
825     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
826     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
827     KEY, "No_Key")
828
829     note(1,
830     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
831     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_078: Power off VIR instrument."\\
832     ),
833     spawn(1,
834     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
835     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,

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836     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
837     ),
838     note(2,
839         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
840         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_078: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
841     ),
842 end;
843
844 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_079,
845     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079-02:33:00,
846     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
847     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
848     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
849     KEY, "No_Key")
850
851     spawn(1,
852         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
853         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
854         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
855     ),
856     note(1,
857         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
858         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOn_079: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
859     ),
860 end;
861
862 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_079,
863     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079-02:23:00,
864     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
865     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
866     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
867     KEY, "No_Key")
868
869     command(1,
870         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
871         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_079: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
872         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
873     ),
874     command(2,
875         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
876         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_079: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN." \,
877         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
878     ),
879     note(1,
880         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
881         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOn_079: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3
882         hour waiting." \
883     ),
884 end;
885
886 request(VIR_C2E_C4S10penCover_079,
887     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079+00:38:00,
888     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
889     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
890     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
891     KEY, "No_Key")
892
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892     activity(1,
893         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
894         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1OpenCover_079: Set for opening the cover."\\,
895         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
896     ),
897 end;
898
899 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079,
900     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079+00:40:00,
901     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
902     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
903     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
904     KEY, "No_Key")
905
906     command(1,
907         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
908         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
909         detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\\,
910         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
911     ),
912     command(2,
913         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
914         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\\,
915         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
916         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
917     ),
918     command(3,
919         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
920         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
921         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
922     ),
923     note(1,
924         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
925         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\\
926     ),
927     command(4,
928         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
929         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
930         detector,150 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\\,
931         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,48,125,5,1,67,150,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
932     ),
933     command(5,
934         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
935         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\\,
936         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
937         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
938     ),
939     command(6,
940         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
941         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
942         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
943     ),
944     note(2,
945         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
946         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C4S1PushbroomToVIR_079: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\\
947     ),

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946 end;
947
948 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_079,
949         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079+01:07:30,
950         TITLE, "VIR close cover",
951         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
952         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
953         KEY, "No_Key")
954
955     activity(1,
956             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
957             NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CloseCover_079: Set for closing the cover." \,
958             VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
959     ),
960 end;
961
962 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_079,
963         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079+01:09:05,
964         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
965         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
966         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
967         KEY, "No_Key")
968
969     command(1,
970             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
971             NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_079: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
972             VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
973     ),
974     command(2,
975             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
976             NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_079: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
977             VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
978     ),
979     note(1,
980         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
981         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1CryocoolerOff_079: the cryocooling is off." \
982     ),
983 end;
984
985 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_079,
986         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079+01:10:05,
987         TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
988         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
989         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
990         KEY, "No_Key")
991
992     command(1,
993             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
994             COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000" \,
995             NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_079: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
996             VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
997     ),
998     command(2,
999             SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1000            NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_079: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1001            VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1002    ),
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1003     note(1,
1004         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1005         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1DumpDataToVR4_079: data volume in VR4 2.820 Gibit."\
1006     ),
1007 end;
1008
1009 request(VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_079,
1010     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079+02:35:05,
1011     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
1012     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1013     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1014     KEY, "No_Key")
1015
1016     note(1,
1017         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1018         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_079: Power off VIR instrument."\
1019     ),
1020     spawn(1,
1021         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1022         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
1023         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
1024     ),
1025     note(2,
1026         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1027         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C4S1PowerOff_079: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
1028     ),
1029 end;
1030
1031 request(VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C4S1LOW,
1032     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_079+02:41:05,
1033     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_c2e_C4S1LOW (ds674)",
1034     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1035     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1036     KEY, "No_Key")
1037
1038     note(1,
1039         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1040         TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds674 - vir_c2e_C4S1LOW"\
1041     ),
1042 end;
1043
1044 $$EOF
```